

4TH WORKSHOP

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
PROGRAMME

PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF CULTURING AND MONITORING PURPLE BACTERIA MIXED AND PURE CULTURES

18TH APRIL 2024

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Dr. Joana Fradinho (Vice Chair and head of the local organizing committee), Dr. Daniel Puyol (Chair), Dr. Gabriel Capson Tojo (Working Group 2 Leader), Dr. Luis Diaz Allegue, WG2 co-Leader, Dr. Raul Muñoz Torre – Grant Awarding Coordinator, Dr. Ioanna Vasiliadou (Training Schools Coordinator)

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INVITED SPEAKERS

BAPTISTE LEROY

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Baptiste Leroy is Associate Professor in the laboratory of proteomic and microbiology of the University of Mons, in Belgium. He studies fundamental aspects of purple bacteria metabolism since a few years now, specifically regarding carbon metabolism and redox homeostasis. The development of PPB based bioprocesses is also now one of his major target, especially in the sector of innovative feed and food sources production and circular economy.

STUDYING AND OPTIMISING YOUR PURPLE PROCESS: BLEND OR PURE ORIGIN?

Every single bioprocess suffers the same internal contradiction: the need for the highest level of performance associated with the lowest cost. The process also need to be highly predictable and resilient. These characteristics are unfortunately poorly compatible and rarely associated to each other. Indeed, predictability and performances are easier to reach with bioprocesses based on pure bacterial strain or at least defined and stable coculture. On the other hand, the use of open communities will significantly decrease the cost of the process and increase its capacity of adaptation.

In Purple Bacteria based biotechnology also this question is particularly important. Multiple processes were developed using specific species and strains at lab scale, but implementation at industrial level of pure culture processes represent a huge challenge in particular in terms of operational cost. In addition, if pure culture can reach very high performances through optimisation, this can only apply to stable conditions of nutrient and light supply or of temperature. When flexibility is required, diversity offered by open community will always be an asset.

On top of this process consideration, it seems today that metabolism is also at play in the contest between pure and mixed culture. We recently observed that the metabolic capabilities of some purple bacteria were apparently influenced by the presence of other strains. The study of cross feeding between purple bacteria communities but also of DNA exchange between them are only starting and will probably reveal another layer of complexity in the resolution of this fundamental question: purple process, blend or pure origin?

TUBA HANDE ERGUDER BAYRAMOĞLU

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Tuba Hande Erguder has been a faculty member at Department of Environmental Engineering, Middle East Technical University, Turkey, since 2009. She received her M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in the same department. She worked as a post-doctoral researcher at Laboratory of Microbial Ecology and Technology (now CMET), Ghent University in 2007-2008. Her main research interest is environmental biotechnology concerning the anaerobic technologies for production of renewable energy and bio-based products, management of municipal and agro-industrial solid wastes / wastewaters, bio-granulation technologies as well as innovative biological nitrogen and microalgal removal systems. Her research bases the integration of microbial consortiums or various reactor operations with a holistic approach in resource recovery, energy production and sustainable waste treatment. She has several peer reviewed publications and conference presentations. In 2014 she won FABED Eser Tümen Outstanding Achievement Award on Environmental Science regarding her studies in anaerobic biotechnology.

INTEGRATION OF PHOTO-FERMENTATION TO DARK FERMENTATION AND METHANOGENESIS TO IMPROVE ENERGY PRODUCTION

Hydrogen is a significant energy carrier and the cleanest fuel of all known fuels. When it is produced from wastes via dark fermentation (DF) and photofermentation (PF), it becomes even more valuable because fossil fuels are not used in these processes and the sustainable environment and development approaches are realized. Yet there are some disadvantages of these processes to be economic in application. The major problem in biohydrogen production is the low H₂ production yields and rates leading to the requirement of large volumes and long retention times. The research topics such as development of reactor configurations, sludge immobilization, genetic modifications in microbial cultures, application of two-stage systems, pretreatment of raw materials have been studied to improve H₂ production. The most suitable raw material types, pretreatment methods, operational conditions/modes, culture types and process configurations are still among the topics significant to be investigated. The most effective configuration type for DF-PF integration is still not certain.

Integration is the combination or hybridization of the systems. It is defined as one of the key categories in smart energy solutions, where highly efficient, cost effective and resilient integrated systems with better resource use and environment could be achieved. In this talk, the results of a project, where a novel three-stage integrated system was developed as a proof of concept, will be presented. Three-stage system, where a methanogenesis (M) stage was integrated between DF and PF stages, will be compared to two-stage DF-PF and DF-M systems in terms of total energy produced per unit substrate (kJ/g sCOD_{added}). The effect of M stage and three-stage system on the improvement of energy yield and productivity, and optimum configuration leading to the highest energy production per unit substrate will be questioned. The opportunities and limitations of two- and three-stage systems will be also discussed.

ROBERTO DE PHILIPPIS

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Roberto De Philippis was Professor of Microbial Biotechnology at the University of Florence, Italy until his retirement, in November 2022. He was Visiting Professor at the Wuhan University, China. He was President of the International Society for Applied Phycology (ISAP) and currently is member of the Supervisory Board of ISAP. He is Associate Editor of the Journal of Applied Phycology; member of the Board of Directors of the International Society for Environmental Biotechnology (ISEB); member of the Experts group of the Section on Environmental Biotechnology of the European Federation of Biotechnology. He was President of the Master Course on Biotechnology for environmental management and sustainable agriculture (BIO-EMSA) at the University of Florence (2017-2021).

His research activity was mainly concerned with the physiology and the possible biotechnological exploitation of phototrophic microorganisms, in particular for the production of biopolymers and bioenergy. He published over than 140 papers (130 indexed in Scopus, H index = 44; citations 6800), 16 chapters in books, he edited 1 book and 3 Special Issues of scientific Journals, participated in more than 180 international and national congresses and filed one national patent.

In 2019 and 2020 he has been included among the world 2% top scientists according to the PLoS Biology ranking.

PHOTOBIOREACTOR DESIGN AND ILLUMINATION SYSTEMS FOR H₂ PRODUCTION WITH PURPLE PHOTOTROPHIC BACTERIA (PPB)

Hydrogen is considered a clean, renewable, and energy-efficient fuel. However, in order to be considered a fuel effectively utilizable at an industrial level, key issues about its economically and environmentally sustainable production have still to be solved. In this regard, microbial hydrogen production, a process with a low environmental impact, has been proposed as an effective and sustainable solution for integrating non biological H₂-producing processes. Among the H₂ producing microbial systems, PPB has been frequently claimed as very promising owing to (i) their high theoretical substrate-to-hydrogen conversion yields, (ii) their lack of O₂-evolving activity, (iii) their capability to metabolize organic substrates derivable from industrial or agricultural residues.

However, the energy input for the biological processes is still higher than the energy output in the form of H₂ gas. One possibility for improving this ratio is to increase the efficiency of the process while at the same time reducing electricity consumption, both of which relate to the issue of an optimal photobioreactor design.

This lecture focuses on recent advances made in photobioreactor design towards higher light to H₂ conversion efficiency, a greater hydrogen production rate and substrate conversion in hydrogen production processes carried out with PPB, giving particular attention to the light source and to illumination protocols. Recent achievements in outdoor hydrogen production in large scale photobioreactors are also reviewed.

HAIFENG LU

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HAIFENG LU, the Associate professor of China Agricultural University and the visiting scholar of University of Illinois at Urban-Champaign. She obtained her doctoral degree in Harbin Institute of Technology. Dr Lu focus on photosynthetic bacteria wastewater treatment and resource recovery technology, the new energy production from agricultural and municipal biowaste and the application of photosynthetic bacteria in agricultural area. She has hosted 1 National Key R&D Program International Intergovernmental Cooperation Project, 1 National Natural Science Foundation of China and 1 Province Key R&D Plan and 5 enterprise cooperation projects those are all about photosynthetic bacteria and microalgae. She had rich international cooperation experiences, she participated 2 International (Regional) and Cooperation and Exchange Program, and regional joint fund of the National Natural Science Foundation of China, 2 Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and other 3 foreign experts projects. She had published more than 40 peer reviewed journal paper and a book “Photosynthetic Bacteria Wastewater Treatment Technology” (in Chinese) and “Gas Biofuels from Waste Biomass” as the first and corresponding author.

NON-TOXIC WASTEWATER RESOURCE RECOVERY BY USING PHOTOSYNTHETIC BACTERIA

Haifeng Lu 1, 2, 3*, Xueyan Liu 1, 2, 3, Changjie Wang 1, 2, Xiaodan Wang 1, 2, Guangming Zhang 4

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2. Key Laboratory of Agricultural Engineering in Structure and Environment, Ministry of Agriculture, Beijing, 100083, China;
3. Sanya Institute of China Agricultural University, Sanya 572025, China;
4. School of Energy and Environmental Engineering, Hebei University of Technology, Tianjin 300401, China

With recent shortages of water, energy, and resources in the world, generating useable products from wastewater has become a new trend. Recovering nutrients from waste streams to produce useful bioresources by using photosynthetic bacteria (PSB) is one of the new developing technologies [1]. Food processing wastewater, including soybean, sugar, starch, brewery wastewater which non-toxic and contain lots of polysaccharides, protein and fatty acids nutrients with pure PSB strains inoculation might be a desirable solution for simultaneously realizing resource recovery from waste streams and promoting the people's acceptance of the PSB materials from waste streams. In this work, we totally summarized our work over the past decades and proposed some new recent discoveries.

Last decades results [2] showed that non-toxic wastewater is desirable for culture PSB, especially the sugar wastewater and soybean wastewater. However, the pure PSB colonize are limit on the function of the purification of wastewater treatment. By using PSB-membrane Bioreactor system can solve this problem. For the processing, principal component analysis results showed that the optimal light intensity was 1500-4000 lux and natural light and tungsten are beneficial for biomass accumulation (Figure 1). Recently, we found that the supplementation of oxygen alternatively could promoted the bioresources production in the non-toxic wastewater-pure PSB cultivation system.

With this strategy, the biomass, bacteriochlorophyll and carotenoids concentration increased by above 20% than those by using traditional strategies. In addition, alternative oxygen supplementation also kept the dominance of PSB strains and kept the stability of the whole system (Figure 2).

In addition, flashing light also takes effect on the photoheterotrophic organisms-PSB[3]. Flashing light also can alleviate the photoinhibition and promote PSB biomass accumulation under high light provision condition. This light regulation strategy could be used to enhance biomass accumulation, bioreactor design and reduce energy consumption in PSB-based industry.

Figure 1. The analysis of wastewater types and light sources for PSB growth

Figure 2. The microbial community composition at genus level of the initial strain and three oxygen supplementation strategies and Correlation network at genus level of the initial strain and three oxygen supplementation strategies, a, original strains; b, anaerobic light groups; c, continuous oxygen supplementation with light groups; d, alternative oxygen supplementation with light group

References

- [1] Capson-Tojo G, Batstone D J, Grassino M, Vlaeminck S E, Puyol D, Verstraete W, Kleerebezem R, Oehmen A, Ghimire A, Pikaar I, Lema J M, Hülsen T, Purple phototrophic bacteria for resource recovery: Challenges and opportunities, *Biotechnology Advances*, 2020, 43: 107567.
- [2] H Lu, G Zhang, Z Zheng, F Meng, T Du, S He, Bio-conversion of photosynthetic bacteria from non-toxic wastewater to realize wastewater treatment and bioresource recovery: A review, *Bioresource Technology*, 2019, 278, 383-399.
- [3] H Lu, R Zhao, C Wang, G Zhang, C Chen, B Li, T Han, Exploration of flashing light interaction effect on improving biomass, protein, and pigments production in photosynthetic bacteria wastewater treatment, *Journal of Clean Production*, 2022, 348, 131304.

4TH WORKSHOP

PROGRAMME

**PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF
CULTURING AND MONITORING
PURPLE BACTERIA MIXED AND
PURE CULTURES**

18TH APRIL 2024

8:30
9:00

REGISTRATION

9:00
13:00

FIRST SESSION

9:00
10:00

Dr. Baptiste Leroy

Key-note speaker

Professor, Department of Proteomics and Microbiology, Université de Mons
Studying and optimising your purple princess: blend or pure origin?

10:00
10:30

Dr. Tuba Hande Erguder

Invited speaker

Professor, Department of Environmental Engineering, Middle East Technical University
Integration of photo-fermentation to dark fermentation and methanogenesis to improve energy production

10:30
11:15

Oral Presentation

Oral presentations from applicants (12 min presentations + 3 min questions)

10:30 **Manon Gilson**, Guillaume Bayon-Vicente, Ruddy Wattiez, Baptiste Leroy

Assimilation of sucrose and its derivatives by Rhodospirillum rubrum and Rhodobacter capsulatus

10:45 **Rossella Labarile**, Maria Varsalona, Danilo Vona, Maria Teresa Melillo, Paolo Stufano, Chiara Mongiovi, Roberto Comparelli, Massimo Trotta

Dopamine effect on growth and morphology of the photosynthetic bacterium Rhodobacter sphaeroides

11:00 **Simone Krings**, Ruddy Wattiez, Baptiste Leroy

11:15 *Valorisation of organic waste for the production of high-value molecules*

11:15 - 11:45 Coffee-Break

11:45
13:00

Oral Presentation

Oral presentations from applicants (12 min presentations + 3 min questions)

- 11:45** **Sergio J. González Camara**, Luis Díaz Allegue, Siegfried E. Vlaeminck
12:00
Optimizing Protein and PHA Production in Purple Non-Sulphur Bacteria in a Pilot-Scale photobioreactor
- 12:00** **Naïm Blansaer**, Sergio González Cámara, Luis D. Allegue, Siegfried E. Vlaeminck and Arno G.B. Wouters
12:15
Extraction and characterization of microbial protein from phototrophic purple bacteria as a sustainable food ingredient
- 12:15** Victor Galve, **Amanda Prado**, Fernando Martínez, Raúl Molin,
12:30 Daniel Puyol
Photo-bio-electro-Fenton: a novel strategy for the complete abatement of industrial wastewater at low cost
- 12:30** **Fernando Muniesa-Merino**, Carlos Manchon, Abraham Esteve-Nuñez
12:45
Photo-electroheterotrophic production of microbial biomass from brewery wastewater in purple phototrophic bacteria is enhanced in fluid-like cathodes
- 12:45** **Xiaodan Wang**, Shichao He, Haifeng Lu, Jean-Philippe Steyer,
13:00 Gabriel Capson-Tojo, Guangming Zhang
Effect of oxygen supplementation strategies on microbial community succession and carbon and nitrogen metabolism in photosynthetic bacteria wastewater resource system

13:00 -14:30 Lunch Break

14:30
16:00

SECOND SESSION

14:30
15:30

Dr. Roberto De Philippis

Key-note speaker

Professor, Department of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Forestry (DAGRI) - University of Florence

Photobioreactor design and illumination systems for H₂ production with PNSB

15:30
16:00

Dr. Haifeng Lu

Invited speaker

China Agricultural University and The Key Laboratory of Agricultural Engineering in Structure and Environment, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs of People's Republic of China

Food Processing Wastewater Resource Production by Using Photosynthetic bacteria

16:00

Oral Presentation

16:30

Oral presentations from applicants (12 min presentations + 3 min questions)

16:00 **Dimitra Matziri**, Nikolaos Remmas, Konstantinos Christoforidis, Ioanna Vasiliadou, Paraschos Melidis, Spyridon Ntougias
16:15 *Enhancing Hydrogen Production from Cheese Whey: A Comparative Study of Dark and Photo Fermentation Bioprocesses*

16:15 **Tugba Keskin-Gungodu**, Patrick C. Hallenbeck
16:30 *Assessing Environmental Sustainability: Life Cycle Analysis of Biohydrogen Production from Sugar Industry Wastes via Photofermentation*

16:30 - 17:00 Coffee-Break

17:00

18:30

ROUND TABLE DISCUSSION

A guide for established protocols for PPB based products including economic prospects

Moderators: Dr. Joana Fradinho (Vice Chair and head of the local organizing committee), Dr. Gabriel Capson Tojo (Working Group 2 Leader).

4TH WORKSHOP

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF
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PURE CULTURES**

ASSIMILATION OF SUCROSE AND ITS DERIVATES BY RHODOSPIRILLUM RUBRUM AND RHODOBACTER CAPSULATUS

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The circular economy has gained increasing attention in recent years. Particularly, the upcycling of liquid by-products of industrial processes rich in organic matter to produce high added-value compounds is promising. Purple non-sulphur bacteria (PNSB) are good candidates for the development of such circular bioprocesses due to their metabolic versatility [1]. Indeed, PNSB were extensively studied for bioindustrial purposes, such as wastewater treatment or the production of bioplastic and biohydrogen [2].

Sugar beet molasses, a co-product from sugar industries, is mainly composed of sucrose (~61%) but also contains fructose and glucose in very low proportions (<1%) [3]. The growth of PNSB on molasses has already been studied, especially in the field of biohydrogen production [4]. However, if macroscopic parameters of their growth have been determined with this carbon source, the sugar assimilation metabolism has been poorly investigated. In this work, we analysed the growth of two strains of PNSB with sucrose as a main carbon source under phototrophic conditions, either in pure culture or in co-culture.

In the case of *Rs. rubrum*, results showed very limited growth through OD680nm monitoring in a sucrose-containing medium (Fig. 1A). However, this strain was able to assimilate fructose and glucose sequentially, with fructose being first assimilated (Fig. 1B). Concerning *Rh. capsulatus*, it was observed that it is capable of assimilating sucrose, fructose and glucose (Figs. 1C and 1D). In co-cultures, bacterial growth reached a final OD680nm of 3.64 ± 0.196 in the presence of sucrose and 3.95 ± 0.179 in the presence of fructose and glucose. Such a high bacterial growth had not yet been observed in pure cultures. Surprisingly, while we have previously shown that this strain was unable to assimilate sucrose, *Rs. rubrum* was still present at the end of the experiment, either in presence of sucrose only or in presence of sucrose, fructose and glucose (Respectively, fig. 1E and 1F, bar graphs). Based on these results, we hypothesised that *Rh. capsulatus* releases organic molecules into the extracellular environment, which would then be assimilated by *rubrum* as a carbon source. A further investigation is required to identify the organic molecule released by *Rh. capsulatus* following sugar assimilation.

Figure 1. Monitoring of growth (blue line) of *Rhodospirillum rubrum* (A,B), *Rhodobacter capsulatus* (C,D) or a co-culture of these two bacterial strains (E,F) cultivated in a medium containing sucrose and previously filtered (A,C,E) or in a medium containing sucrose and its derivatives, previously autoclaved (B,D,F). Red, green and orange lines represent the evolution of sucrose, fructose and glucose concentration, respectively. Bar plots represent the proportion of *Rs. rubrum* (black bars) and *Rh. capsulatus* (hatched bars) at different time points in co-cultures. N = 5

Acknowledgments

The research leading to these results has been funded by the Public Service of Wallonia (Economy, Employment and Research), under the FoodWal agreement n°2210182 from the Win4Excellence project of the Wallonia Recovery Plan.

Proteomic data acquisition was made possible through the support of the European fund for regional development (FEDER) through the Bioprofiling projects cofinanced by EU and Wallonia.

References

- [1] H. Lu, G. Zhang, Shichao He, R. Zhao, and D. Zhu, "Purple non-sulfur bacteria technology: a promising and potential approach for wastewater treatment and bioresources recovery," *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, vol. 37, no. 3, p. 161, 2021
- [2] G. Capson-Tojo et al., "Purple phototrophic bacteria for resource recovery: Challenges and opportunities," *Biotechnol. Adv.*, vol. 43, 2020
- [3] A. Palmomari et al., "Short communication: Characterization of molasses chemical composition," *Dairy Sci.*, vol. 103, no. 7, pp. 6244–6249, 2020
- [4] E. Sagir, E. Ozgur, U. Gunduz, I. Eroglu, and M. Yucel, "Single-stage photofermentative biohydrogen production from sugar beet molasses by different purple non-sulfur bacteria," *Bioprocess Biosyst. Eng.*, vol. 40, 2017

DOPAMINE EFFECT ON GROWTH AND MORPHOLOGY OF THE PHOTOSYNTHETIC BACTERIUM RHODOBACTER SPHAEROIDES

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Living and metabolically active microorganisms can be used for the sustainable production of energy in biohybrid devices [1]. The purple non-sulfur bacterium *Rhodobacter sphaeroides* is a photosynthetic prokaryote able to convert sunlight into other forms of energy by photosynthesis that can be exploited in such biohybrid devices in combination with naturally inspired polymers [2]. Polydopamine, a bioinspired polymer produced by the self-polymerization of dopamine, can be used as bacterial coating due to its excellent adhesivity and low toxicity while its redox-active functional ligands can be exploited for bioelectric applications [2-4]. The biocompatibility of dopamine towards the photosynthetic growth of *R. sphaeroides* was tested after additions of the monomer to the culture media [5]. The effect of DA on the cell morphology and on the accumulation of poly- β -hydroxybutyrate (PHB), a bacterial energy storage material that accumulates in cells in presence of a carbon-rich environment was investigated [6].

References

- [1] R.W. Bradley, P. Bombelli, S.J. Rowden, C.J. Howe. Biological photovoltaics: intra- and extra-cellular electron transport by cyanobacteria. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* (2012) vol. 40, pp. 1302-1307
- [2] R. Labarile, D. Vona, M. Varsalona, M. Grattieri, M. Reggente, R. Comparelli, G.M. Farinola, F. Fischer, A.A. Boghossian, M. Trotta. In vivo polydopamine coating of *Rhodobacter sphaeroides* for enhanced electron transfer. *Nano Research* (2024) vol. 17, pp. 875-881.
- [3] M. Reggente, C. Roullier, M. Mouhib, P. Brandl, H. Wang, S. Tacconi, F. Mura, L. Dini, R. Labarile, M. Trotta, F. Fischer, A.A. Boghossian. Polydopamine-coated photoautotrophic bacteria for improving extracellular electron transfer in living photovoltaics. *Nano Research* (2024), vol. 17, pp. 866-874.
- [4] G. Buscemi, D. Vona, P. Stufano, R. Labarile, P. Cosma, A. Agostiano, M. Trotta, G. Farinola, M. Grattieri. Bio-inspired redox-adhesive polydopamine matrix for intact bacteria biohybrid photoanodes. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* (2022) 14(23), pp. 26631-26641.
- [5] R. Labarile, M. Varsalona, D. Vona, P. Stufano, M. Grattieri, G.M. Farinola, M. Trotta. A novel route for anoxygenic polymerization of dopamine via purple photosynthetic bacteria metabolism. *MRS Advances* (2023), vol. 8, pp. 423-428
- [6] J. Kobayashi, A. Kondo. Disruption of poly (3-hydroxyalkanoate) depolymerase gene and overexpression of three poly (3-hydroxybutyrate) biosynthetic genes improve poly (3-hydroxybutyrate) production from nitrogen rich medium by *Rhodobacter sphaeroides*. *Microbial Cell Factories* (2019) vol. 18, pp. 1-13

VALORISATION OF ORGANIC WASTE FOR THE PRODUCTION OF HIGH-VALUE MOLECULES

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Organic waste treatment by biomethanation could create renewable energy. The process produces biogas, containing around 50% methane and 50% CO₂, and solid/liquid waste (digestate) which contains ammonium and volatile fatty acids (VFA). Due to its high nitrogen contents, the digestate is currently used as fertiliser [1]. However, the high levels of VFA in digestates allow valorisation by purple non-sulfur bacteria, whose versatile metabolism allows the production of single-cell proteins, of bioplastics (polyhydroxyalkanoates or PHA) or of carotenoids and hydrogen [2]. *Rhodospirillum rubrum* has been the centre of interest for the studies of purple bacteria in our laboratory. In addition, co-cultures containing *Rs. rubrum*, *Rhodobacter capsulatus* and *Cereibacter sphaeroides* were used. First, a culture medium containing 40% acetate, 20% propionate, 15% butyrate, 5% isobutyrate, 10% valerate and 10% isovalerate as carbon sources (synthetic digestate) was used to monitor the assimilation of these VFA by the purple bacteria. Acetate and propionate were assimilated rapidly, while isovaleric acid was assimilated last (Figure 1). Mimicking digestate ammonium levels in the synthetic digestate resulted in no growth inhibition at a twofold increased concentration of NH₄Cl, while a tenfold increase led to severely reduced bacterial growth in *Rs. rubrum* cultures and in the co-cultures.

In the next phase, digestate from an anaerobic digestion using kitchen waste will be used to assess the effects on the bacterial growth while optimising the production of PHA and carotenoids.

This research is supported by the European fund for regional development (FEDER) through the WalBiopower and Bioprofiling projects cofinanced by EU and Wallonia.

Figure 1. Comparison of the assimilation rate of the different volatile fatty acids (VFA) by *Rhodospirillum rubrum*.

References

- [1] L. Braga Nan, E. Trably, G. Santa-Catalina, N. Bernet, J.-P. Delgenès, and R. Escudéi, 'Biomethanation processes: new insights on the effect of a high H₂ partial pressure on microbial communities', *Biotechnol. Biofuels*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 141, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s13068-020-01776-y.
- [2] A. Alloul, N. Blansaer, P. Cabecas Segura, R. Wattiez, S. E. Vlaeminck, and B. Leroy, 'Dehazing redox homeostasis to foster purple bacteria biotechnology', *Trends Biotechnol.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 106-119, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.tibtech.2022.06.010.

OPTIMIZING PROTEIN AND PHA PRODUCTION IN PURPLE NON-SULPHUR BACTERIA IN A PILOT-SCALE PHOTOBIOREACTOR

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The sustainable production of microbial proteins and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) as alternatives to conventional agricultural and petrochemical products necessitates scalable and efficient biotechnological processes. Purple non-sulphur bacteria (PNSB), such as *Rhodobacter capsulatus*, exhibit versatile metabolic capabilities for the concurrent biosynthesis of these valuable bioproducts under photoheterotrophic conditions [1,2]. However, data on pilot-scale production and downstream processing is still scarce, which limits its technological development.

Employing a 215 L photo-tubular bioreactor, *R. capsulatus* was cultured with acetate as the primary carbon source over a three-month period. The experimental design varied organic loading rates and nutrient availability, specifically examining the effects of ammonium limitation on PHA accumulation and protein synthesis. The dual objective was to elucidate the optimal conditions for maximizing PHA content without compromising protein production. Preliminary results showed high PHA accumulation even under high nutrient conditions, achieving a maximum PHA of 31% DW, with a concurrent protein content of 45% CDW.

Downstream processing of the production was investigated, accounting for a biomass recovery of 80%, using a pilot-scale continuous disc centrifuge for biomass dewatering with a centrate with the remaining 20% of the biomass that could be recovered by membrane separation. Furthermore, we have studied different drying processes (freeze-drying and spray-drying) to analyze the properties of the bioproducts separately and analysed separation by bead-milling and solid-liquid separation where we obtained a solid fraction with 95% of PHA and a liquid proteinaceous fraction with a recovery of up to 60%.

This investigation contributes to the scalable application of PNSB in biotechnology, offering insights into the operational parameters and processing techniques critical for the industrial viability of microbial protein and PHA production.

References

- [1] Allegue LD, Ventura M, Melero JA, Puyol D. Unraveling PHA production from urban organic waste with purple phototrophic bacteria via organic overload. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2022;166:112687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112687>.
- [2] Hülsen T, Venturato D, Chan C, Vandi L, Laycock B, Pratt S, et al. Polyhydroxyalkanoate production in a biofilm by mixed culture phototrophic bacteria. *J Clean Prod* 2024;434:140001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.140001>.

EXTRACTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROBIAL PROTEIN FROM PHOTOTROPHIC PURPLE BACTERIA AS A SUSTAINABLE FOOD INGREDIENT

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Meeting the increasing global demand for protein in a sustainable way presents a critical challenge for the food system. With concerns over the environmental impact of animal protein production, there is a pressing need for alternative protein sources. Microbial protein derived from phototrophic purple bacteria, which can grow on nutrients from carbon capture and utilization, emerges as a promising solution [1]. However, while dried biomass from purple bacteria has shown potential as a feed ingredient, its suitability for food applications hinges not only on nutritional quality but also on functional properties like foaming, gelation, and emulsification, which significantly influence texture and sensory appeal. Protein structural properties such as molecular weight and hydrophobicity distribution, and physical properties such as the degree of denaturation and solubility are crucial in determining these functional attributes [2]. However, these characteristics have not been previously measured for purple bacteria-derived protein. Also, the availability of these proteins, which can be increased by cell wall disruption, will determine their function. This presentation, therefore, aims to extract and characterize these proteins for the first time.

This study investigates the extraction yield and protein denaturation of two types of purple bacteria biomass: *Rhodobacter capsulatus* grown on acetate, and a co-culture of *Rhodospirillum rubrum* and *Cereibacter sphaeroides* grown on ethanol, both under axenic conditions. Both biomasses underwent two treatments: freeze-drying alone, and freeze-drying followed by bead milling under cryogenic conditions. Upon aqueous extraction at pH 9, protein extraction yields of 6% for *Rb. capsulatus* and 9% for the co-culture were obtained, for the freeze-dried only material. Bead-milled biomass exhibited significantly higher extraction yields, reaching 29% at pH 9 and 39% at pH 8 for *Rb. capsulatus* and the co-culture, respectively. Differential scanning calorimetry revealed denaturation temperatures between 65°C and 75°C for both biomasses. These findings hold significant promise for advancing research into the functional properties of proteins from purple bacteria, though further research of the structural properties is needed, such as molecular weight distribution.

References

- [1] Alloul, A., Spanoghe, J., Machado, D., & Vlaeminck, S. E. (2022). Unlocking the genomic potential of aerobes and phototrophs for the production of nutritious and palatable microbial food without arable land or fossil fuels. *Microbial biotechnology*, 15(1), 6-12.
- [2] Wouters, A. G., Rombouts, I., Fierens, E., Brijs, K., & Delcour, J. A. (2016). Relevance of the functional properties of enzymatic plant protein hydrolysates in food systems. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 15(4), 786-800.

PHOTO-BIO-ELECTRO-FENTON: A NOVEL STRATEGY FOR THE COMPLETE ABATEMENT OF INDUSTRIAL WASTEWATER AT LOW COST

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Rapid population growth and higher living standards have heightened freshwater consumption, escalating environmental pollution. This necessitates advanced water treatment technologies for efficient conservation and reuse. [1].

Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), particularly electrochemical advanced oxidation processes (EAOPs), like bio-electro-Fenton (BEF) systems, show high efficiency in treating industrial wastewater [2], including refinery wastewater. BEF combines a bio-electrochemical system with electro-Fenton oxidation, enabling in-situ reagent production, reducing operational costs, and mitigating risks linked to hydrogen peroxide transportation or storage for the Fenton reaction [1,3].

We propose a novel approach, the photo-bio-electro-Fenton (PBEF) technology. In this system, electroactive purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) utilize infrared light to oxidize organic matter, growing under photoheterotrophic conditions. PPB transfer electrons extracellularly to a carbonaceous electrode, producing an electric current for the Fenton reaction [4, 5]. In the cathodic chamber, oxygen combines with electrons and protons to create oxygenated water. Upon interacting with iron, this water dissociates, forming hydroxyl radicals that address recalcitrant compounds not degraded by bacteria, achieving complete mineralization of contaminants [3].

Figure 1. Performance of a photo-bio-electro-Fenton reactor(photo refinery).

References

- [1] S. M. Sathé, I. Chakraborty, B. K. Dubey, and M. M. Ghangrekar, *Environ Res*, vol. 204, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.112135.
- [2] C. Barrera-Díaz, P. Canizares, F. J. Fernández, R. Natividad, M. A. Rodrido, *Journal of the Mexican chemical society*, vol. 58, pp. 256-275, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.29356/jmcs.v58i3.133.
- [3] M. Kahoush, N. Behary, A. Cayla, and V. Nierstrasz, *Process Biochemistry*, vol. 64, Elsevier Ltd, pp. 237-247, Jan. 01, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.procbio.2017.10.003.
- [4] K. Beaver, E. M. Gaffney, and S. D. Minter, *Electrochim Acta*, vol. 416, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.electacta.2022.140291.
- [5] X. Qi, Y. Ren, P. Liang, and X. Wang, *Bioresour Technol*, vol. 258, Elsevier Ltd, pp. 310-317, Jun. 01, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2018.03.058.

PHOTO-ELECTROHETEROTROPHIC PRODUCTION OF MICROBIAL BIOMASS FROM BREWERY WASTEWATER IN PURPLE PHOTOTROPHIC BACTERIA IS ENHANCED IN FLUID-LIKE CATHODES

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Due to its metabolic versatility, mixed cultures of purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) could be exploited for the production of added value products such as microbial biomass, H₂ and polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), not only with a variety of carbon sources but interacting with an electrode as well 1. For PHB production, Microbial electrosynthesis (MES) has already been proved as a suitable strategy under photoautotrophic conditions 2. In contrast with classical biofilm-based techniques previously reported in electromicrobial studies, we have demonstrated that a fluid-like electrode can directly accept or donate electrons to the metabolism of planktonic PPB and enhance the biodegradation rate of brewery wastewater 3.

In this work, a mixed PPB culture enriched from brewery wastewater was cultured under photoheterotrophic conditions in an electrochemical fluidized bed reactor with glassy carbon 10% v/v as the electron donor and high and low reduced wastewater separately incubated. The electrochemical bioreactor was poised at different electrochemical potential values as a mean to evaluate i) microbial biomass production ii) wastewater biodegradation rate.

Chemical oxygen degradation reached a maximum value of 90% in high and low wastewater at a polarization value of -0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl reference electrode. For biomass production, higher values were achieved at more negative polarization values in contrast with Open Circuit Potential conditions. Even though a strong interaction with the electrode was not observed, the polarization might had an effect as a redox potential controller comparable with an electrofermentation process 4.

References

- [1] Vasiliadou, I. A. et al. Biological and Bioelectrochemical Systems for Hydrogen Production and Carbon Fixation Using Purple Phototrophic Bacteria. *Front. Energy Res.* 6, (2018).
- [2] Ranaivoarisoa, T. O., Singh, R., Rengasamy, K., Guzman, M. S. & Bose, A. Towards sustainable bioplastic production using the photoautotrophic bacterium *Rhodospseudomonas palustris* TIE-1. *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 46, 1401–1417 (2019).
- [3] Manchon, C. et al. Fluid-like electrodes and Purple Phototrophic Bacteria: bridging the gap in wastewater biorefineries. *Chem. Eng. J.* 453, 139828 (2023).
- [4] Virdis, B. et al. Electro-fermentation: Sustainable bioproductions steered by electricity. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 59, 107950 (2022).

EFFECT OF OXYGEN SUPPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES ON MICROBIAL COMMUNITY SUCCESSION AND CARBON AND NITROGEN METABOLISM IN PHOTOSYNTHETIC BACTERIA WASTEWATER RESOURCE SYSTEM

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Given the problem that continuous oxygen supplementation would weaken the photosynthetic bacteria (PSB) domination in the microbial community of PSB wastewater resource utilization system [1, 2], a 12 h- anaerobic/12 h- oxygen supplementation intermittent oxygen supplementation strategy (A/M-O) was proposed based on the special metabolic interaction mechanism of photophosphorylation and oxidative phosphorylation in PSB. Among A/M-O, continuous anaerobic (A-O), and continuous oxygen supplementation (M-O) strategies, the differences of PSB resource recovery and microbial community characteristics and functions were compared, and the mechanism of oxygen affecting carbon and nitrogen metabolism was analyzed.

The results showedthat A/M-O significantly improved PSB biomass concentration (2419.3 mg/L) and protein concentration (1411.5mg/L). Compared with A-O and M-O, the biomass concentration of A/M-O increased by 76.4% and 26.4%, while the protein concentration increased by 67.4% and 40.5%.In addition, A/M-O and M-O significantly enhanced chemical oxygen demand (COD), ammonia (NH₄+N) removal, and protein content. Under the above three oxygen supplementation strategies, the bacterial community structure was significantly different: the relative abundance of Ectothiorhodospira (the only PSB species in the system)under A/M-O condition increased to 78.0 %, which was 1.5 and 4.4 times higher than that under A-O and M-O conditions. The Ace and Chao indexes, the number of "nodes" and "connections", and the positive correlation ratio of the microbial network in the M-O and A/M-O strategies were all higher than those in the A-O strategy, indicating that the M-O and A/M-O were conducive to maintaining the stability of microbial community structure and function. Tax4Fun functional prediction showed that A/M-O increased biomass and protein concentration by promoting the relative abundance of key enzymes encoding genes in the EMP pathway and TCA cycle; M-O and A/M-O improved the COD and NH₄+N removal, and protein content by increasing the relative abundance of carbon metabolism and nitrogen metabolism key enzymes encoding genes and changing the oxidative redox potential (ORP).

The results of this study innovate the methods of maintaining the dominance of PSB, improving the stability of PSB consortium structure and function in PSB wastewater resource utilization system.

Figure 1. Effect of oxygen supplementation strategies on microbial community succession and carbon and nitrogen metabolism in photosynthetic bacteria wastewater resource system

References

- [1] A. Allou, M. Muys, N. Hertoghs, F.M. Kerckhof, S.E. Vlaeminck. 2021. Cocultivating aerobic heterotrophs and purple bacteria for microbial protein sequential photo- and chemotrophic reactors. *Bioresour Technol*, 319, 124192.
- [2] G. Capson-Tojo, S. Lin, D.J. Batstone, T. Hulsen. 2021. Purple phototrophic bacteria are outcompeted by aerobic heterotrophs in the presence of oxygen. *Water Res*, 194, 116941.

ENHANCING HYDROGEN PRODUCTION FROM CHEESE WHEY: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DARK AND PHOTO FERMENTATION BIOPROCESSES

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The extended consumption of fossil fuels has adverse environmental impact (greenhouse gas emissions) and can lead to economic instability. In this framework, biohydrogen production from agricultural and food industry wastewater, such as cheese whey wastewater, through fermentation has drawn worldwide attention, since it is an adequate source for energy recovery. Biohydrogen has been recognized as a cost-effective and clean energy source, as it has high energy content, about 2.75 times higher than other conventional hydrocarbon fuels, and its combustion releases only water [1]. Dark fermentation is the main biochemical process to break down the organic content of cheese whey, while exploiting its organics for biohydrogen production [2]. However, application of volatile dark fermentation for this purpose is a challenging issue, due to its low hydrogen yield and the accumulation of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) and low molecular weight (MW) alcohols. Moreover, the bioconversion of volatile fatty acids into biomass, H₂ and CO₂ via purple phototrophic bacteria can be considered as a promising alternative approach to enhance biohydrogen production from organic wastewaters [3].

In this study, the efficiency of dark- and photo-fermentation processes to produce biohydrogen from cheese whey wastewater was investigated. In particular, two laboratory-scale twin batch reactors, with a working volume of 1.8 L each, were installed and operated under dark and photosynthetic (as created with infrared light) conditions. The bioreactors were operated under mesophilic conditions (34°C) and the reduction of COD and carbohydrates was monitored at various time intervals. Specifically, total COD remained stable in the dark fermentation and equal to 3 g/L, whereas COD in the photobioreactor was reduced to 3.0 g/L to 2.4 g/L. The carbohydrate content reduced from 0.41 g/L and 0.44 g/L to 0.06 g/L and 0.02 g/L during dark and photo fermentation respectively. Biogas production was much higher in the photofermentation system compared to the bioreactor performing dark fermentation. The results indicate that photofermentation carried out by purple phototrophic bacteria is an effective route for the valorization of real wastewater through energy recovery.

References

- [1] A. I., Osman, T. J., Deka, D. C., Baruah, D. W., Rooney, Critical challenges in biohydrogen production processes from the organic feedstocks. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery* 13(10), (2020).
- [2] J. S., Gokhale, D. P., Tekale, U. S., Annapure, Biohydrogen Production Using Cheese Industry Waste: Current Trends and Challenges, *Organic Waste to Biohydrogen* Chapter, (2022).
- [3] R., Rao, N. Basak, Fermentative molecular biohydrogen production from cheese whey: present prospects and future strategy, *Appl Biochem Biotechnol* 193, 2297–2330, (2021).

ASSESSING ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY: LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS OF BIOHYDROGEN PRODUCTION FROM SUGAR INDUSTRY WASTES VIA PHOTOFERMENTATION

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Among the different biohydrogen production methods, photofermentative biohydrogen production has been recognized as one of the most environmentally friendly technologies. One of the biggest advantages of biohydrogen production by photofermentation is that organic wastes can be used. During photo-fermentation, anaerobic photofermentative bacteria utilize Volatile Fatty Acids (VFA) as a carbon source in the presence of light to generate hydrogen gas [1]. One advantage of the photo-fermentation technique is the high conversion rate of organic acids. However, utilizing light can significantly raise costs due to the subsequent rise in energy usage. Unlike the studies on biohydrogen production from VFA-containing wastewaters in the literature, in a previous study conducted by us, 8 mol H₂/mol sucrose production was achieved from sugar industry wastes without the need for pre-treatment or additional dark fermentation step. Among organic wastes, the sugar industry is important in many countries and its organic-rich wastes can be utilized in many fields. Beet molasses and blackstrap molasses are significant byproducts of the sugar industry. Both substances have a significant amount of sucrose, which makes them appropriate for the biological production of hydrogen [2].

The way to quantitatively demonstrate the environmental friendliness of any technology, which is said to be environmentally friendly, is through detailed life cycle analysis. This study analysed the environmental impact of biohydrogen production from sugar industry wastes. The life cycle assessment was performed using the data from our previous study for inventory analysis in Open LCA. Ecoinvent database and CML Baseline impact method were used for a detailed environmental analysis [3].

Within the scope of this study, a mini-review of LCA applications in the literature on biohydrogen production by photofermentation will be conducted. Then a life cycle analysis will be performed on the previous data in the gate-to-gate system boundaries. Through LCA, hot spots in the processes will be identified and the environmental impacts (global warming, eutrophication, acidification..etc) of photofermentative biohydrogen production from sugar industry wastewater will be examined comparatively and in detail.

References

- [1] Keskin T., Abo-Hashesh M., Hallenbeck P. C., (2011), "Photofermentative hydrogen production from wastes" *Bioresource Technology*. 102 (18): 8557-8568.
- [2] Keskin T., Hallenbeck P.C., (2012), "Hydrogen production from sugar industry wastes using single-stage photofermentation", *Bioresource Technology*, 112: 131-136.
- [3] Morya, R., Raj, T., Lee, Y., Pandey, A. K., Kumar, D., Singhania, R. R., ... & Kim, S. H. (2022). Recent updates in biohydrogen production strategies and life-cycle assessment for sustainable future. *Bioresource technology*, 128159.

The workshop is organized by Dr. Joana Fradinho (Vice Chair and head of the local organizing committee), Dr. Daniel Puyol (Chair), Dr. Gabriel Capson Tojo (Working Group 2 Leader), Dr. Luis Diaz Allegue, WG2 co-Leader, Dr. Raul Muñoz Torre – Grant Awarding Coordinator, Dr. Ioanna Vasiliadou (Training Schools Coordinator), in the frame of WG 2: Resource recovery from waste and wastewater and downstream procedures for PPB biomass of the COST action (CA21146) – PURPLEGAIN.

PURPLEGAIN also aims to create a database for techno-economic, social and environmental impacts studies, which facilitates the marketability of both the PPB-based technologies and the products to extract. Some focused products are polyhydroxyalkanoates, single-cell proteins, biomass for energy, biomass as fertilizer, biohydrogen, carotenoids, terpenoids, organic acids, coenzyme Q10, and 5-aminolevulinic acid.

Accordingly, the workshop in the frame of Working Group 2, which coordinates the initiatives focused on applied research, exploring operational strategies for combined product development, is focused on two main Topics:

1. Wastewater treatment with purple phototrophic bacteria and resource recovery from organic waste sources in purple photo-biorefineries
2. Downstream processing: advances in extraction and purification of high added-value molecules, and engineering challenges: scale-up of photo-bioreactors, including control and light integration.

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